

A Trial Manufacturing Study of FRP Bicycle

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ABSTRACT

In order to make clear the mechanical properties of FRP bicycle, a study was carried out and some of the experimental data connected with the trial manufacture of FRP bicycle are presented.

This report consists of two sections, one dealing with the investigation on a Bowden FRP bicycle, and the other with the trial manufacturing study of our FRP bicycle. The Bowden bicycle did not show any excellent mechanical strength nor smooth handling stability. At the beginning of the trial manufacturing of our FRP bicycle, the study on the proper selection of basic glass material was made by way of the mechanical strength tests (tensile and bending tests) on various materials. The combination of SLS-213 (satin) 2 ply and CM305 (chopstrand mat) 1 ply was found as suitable material for FRP bicycle. The unsaturated Polyester resin was used in this FRP bicycle.

INTRODUCTION

Till now the diamond type bicycle frames has had superior stability on both function and structural dynamics, and this diamond type structure has not been changed. In order to make new design and long life bicycle frame, for advancing the bicycle industrial technology, this manufacturing study of FRP bicycle was carried out.

This paper consists of two sections, one dealing with the investigation on Bowden FRP bicycle, and other on the trial manufacturing study of our FRP bicycle.

AN INVESTIGATION OF BOWDEN FRP BICYCLE

About twenty years ago, The American Bomard Co., Ltd. developed a FRP bicycle named after Bowden and got some public attentions as a new type bicycle in the world. However, as a results of actual riding road tests, it was discovered that this Bowden bicycle has many structural defects. The results obtained in this investigation are summarized as follow:

FRAME STRUCTURE

As shown in Fig.1, in order to reduce number of frame parts and assembly cost, the body, mudguard and chain case are integrated into one body structure, and headlight, buzzer and taillight are installed inside the frame. Also, the frame consisted of two symmetrical shells joined by epoxy resin, and covered by SUS304 stainless steel lace.

The inner structure of this FRP frame were inspected by X-ray photographs. As the results, the principal parts of this frame are shown in Fig.2-4. Fig.2 shows the head portion of the frame, Fig.3 shows the seat section and Fig.4 indicates the hanger section of the frame bottom. From these results obtained in this X-ray examination, it was clear that FRP thickness of each sections were between 1.6 and 2.3mm. However, it was observed that FRP thickness of hanger section was about 5mm and this section was reinforced by 8 FRP ribs. It was also observed that the principal portions (head, seat and hanger section etc.) were reinforced by 1.2mm thickness mild steel plates adhesion, furthermore, head and seat sections were reinforced by 25.4-31.8mm diameter steel pipes and 1.2mm thickness steel plates, and these steel pipes and plates were joined by epoxy resin to both inside of left and right FRP half shells.

MATERIALS USED IN BOWDEN FRAME AND MANUFACTURING PROCESS

The materials used in frame and mudguards are shown as follows:

(1) Resin and filler

Unsaturated polyester resin styrene used as the principal building materials, CaCO_3 was used as the filler for the frame and mudguard.

(2) Glass

About 7-9micron meter diameter X 50mm length chopped strand of electric-non-alkalic glass were used in these frames and mudguards as the principal strength member in this FRP bicycle, and its contents was about 12.5%(wt). Also, the tensile strength of this FRP was about $10.8\text{kg}/\text{mm}^2$ at room temperature under the normal conditions.

MANUFACTURING PROCESS

Right and left two half shells of this FRP frame were produced by hydraulic press forming process and adhesived to each other by epoxy resin at the center line to make the one body complete frame. The surface of this frame was not finely finished by buffing machine or other fine process, and some of glass fibers appeared on the frame surface. Fig.5 shows a photograph of the glass fibers of the frame inspected by microscope.

PERFORMANCE TEST

Riding Test

The results obtained in this road riding test are summarized as follows;

- (1) The trembling action of the Bowden bicycle was very pronounced compared with other 26inch ordinary steel made bicycles and this FRP bicycle had very low rigidity
- (2) The maneuverability of this bicycle was not so good because of larger deformation of FRP frame as compared to the steel made bicycles.
- (3) The vibrations of the frame caused by braking torque was very large and steering ability or handling stability was lower than that of steel bicycle.

Strength Test

Fig.6 shows the scheme of the static load test of the Bowden FRP frame by 400kg max. weight loading on the seat position of the frame. The results obtained in this test are shown in Fig.7. In this figure, black marks(•) show the value of Bowden frame and white marks(o) show that of 26inch steel frame. The torsional strength test of Bowden frame was carried out by using torsional test fixture. Fig.8 shows the results of this test. From this figure, it was clear that the rigidity of the Bowden frame was much less than that of steel frame. Also, the bending test of this frame was conducted by measuring the

frame deflection value by the frame bending test device. Fig.9 shows the results of the bending test.

From these results, it was apparent that various strengths of the Bowden bicycle were not sufficient in comparison with other steel made frames. It seems that this phenomena was caused by insufficient amount of glass fibers in the FRP frame of this bicycle.

Trial Manufacturing of FRP Bicycle

From Bowden bicycle's investigation, the experiment of trial manufacturing of FRP bicycle was carried out according to the following mentioned philosophy.

FUNDAMENTAL EXPERIMENT

Strength of FRP

To obtain some suitable conditions for FRP bicycle, many test pieces were prepared with various glass clothes combinations, and examined under both tensile and bending load tests. The results of both tensile and bending test for these test pieces with each combination of glass clothes are shown in table 1. In this table, number in brackets shows the values under the wet condition. From this results, it was clear that the sandwiched structure of CM305 between two SLS-213 glass clothes exhibited the best condition, among various combinations, and its tensile strength was 27.8kg/mm².

Relation between the Surface Roughness and Tensile Strength

As the same case of Bowden FRP bicycle, to obtain the suitable surface roughness of armature steel plate for fitting to FRP layer many kinds of mild steel specimens having different surface roughness were prepared by various types of emery papers. Fig. 10 shows various roughness values made by 60, 120, 240, 400 and 600 mesh emery paper polishing on the adhesive surface of SS41 mild steel rod(13φx75mm length). To investigate the relation between the surface roughness and adhesive strength, two specimens having same roughness were abutted on the same longitudinal directions line keeping various joint clearance(t=0.1, 0.2, and 0.3mm).

After adhering two specimens with epoxy resin, these specimens were examined by tensile load test. The results obtained in this experiment are shown in Fig.11. From this figure, it was observed that the adhesive strength of the specimens with fine roughness($R_{max}=0.6-0.8$ micronmeter) were stronger than that of other. And also, it was clear that the tensile strength of the specimens having 0.08-0.12mm joint clearance was the highest(about 3.4kg/mm²).

Table 2 shows the roughness values of the polished mild steel surfaces. Fig.12 shows a view of fractured surface at the adhesived zone polished by 600 mesh emery paper.

Design and Manufacturing of FRP Frame

26 inch size right type bicycle frame was trial manufactured according to the above mentioned philosophy and the results of fundamental experiment are given in the following. Fig.13 shows a newly designed FRP bicycle frame. This new FRP frame was trial manufactured by fore mentioned best combination of glass clothes(SLS-213 2ply and CM-305 1ply, and GA20 unsaturated polyester resin). In order to make good fluidity of unsaturated polyester resin, two shell-forming moulds(right and left) were preheated at 35°C by 200 Watt infrared lamps. After the shell-forming operations were completed these right and left shells were cured at 130°C for 24 hrs.

The head, seat and hanger portions of the FRP frame were reinforced by 1.2mm thickness steel plates adhered with epoxy resin. The surface of these plates were polished by 600 mesh emery papers to get strong adhesived joints. In order to make a complete bicycle frame, both right and left half shells were jointed by epoxy resin together with some long fiber glass to get the steady adhesive joint. Further more, to make sure of good joining strength, a small

channel lace made by SUS304 stainless steel was covered on the joint edges. Fig.14 shows the trial manufactured FRP bicycle.

MECHANICAL STRENGTH TESTS OF THE TRIAL MANUFACTURED FRP BICYCLE

Static Load Test and Bending Test

The new manufactured FRP frames examined by static load test and bending test as same as the case of Bowden frame. Fig.15 shows the results of the static load test and Fig.16 shows the results of the bending test.

Vibration Test(Repeated Impact Test)

Also, FRP frames were investigated by vibration-impact test machine(just like in the case of ordinary 26 inch size steel made bicycle frame) according to JIS rule. This machine was operated with one inch height cam shaft driving at 250r.p.m. under 120kg load on the seat position as shown in Fig.17. And in order to pass JIS rule, all bicycles have to endure 10,000 times(40 minutes) of this impact test under above mentioned testing conditions. Five FRP frame were examined by the vibration-impact test machine. The results of this experiment are shown in Fig.18. From this figure, it was clear that five tested FRP frames had had enough durable strength as the endurance time of these frames were all longer than JIS time(40 minutes).

Practical Riding Test

Seven FRP bicycles(randomly chosen among 50 trial manufactured FRP bicycles) were examined by practical riding test on the gravel-paved road. This test was carried out to examine stability of these FRP bicycle over a 1040km total distance during ten days. It was observed that there are no cracks, and fatal defects except for 12-30mm elongation at the wheel base length(elomgate rate: 1.1-1.9%).

DISCUSSION

From the results, it seems that unstability or poor steerability in Bowden bicycle caused by low mechanical strength(tension, bending and rigidity) were caused by short only about 50mm length chop strand glass fibers. However the mechanical strength of 50 trial manufactured FRP bicycle were very excellent because much more glass clothes were used for these frames. From this point, it was considered that the practical bodies of motorcyckes or automobiles could be made by FRP structure, containing average weight of 50 trial manufactured FRP bicycles was 17.2kg. This value was 2-3kg lighter than ordinary 26 inch size steel made bicycle.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions obtained in this experiment are summarized as follows:

- (1) The practical useful FRP bicycle can be made from highly glass cloth structure having enough mechanical strength.
- (2) To obtain strong FRP bicycle, the critical positions of the frame had to be reinforced by thin thickness steel pla estadheshed with epoxy resin.
- (3) To get the strong adhesive joint, the joint surfaces of the steel plates should have fine surfaces($R_{max}=0.6-0.7\mu m$) by using 300-600 mesh emery papers.
- (4) To stop the cracks creation and its propagation at the adhesived joint, both right and left half shells of the frame must be adhesed together with long glass fibers between both shells.
- (5) Concerning bicycle design, it seems that the appearance of the trial manufactured FRP bicycles was much more appreciated compared with the ordinary steel made bicycle, and FRP elements are recommended as the new bicycle making materials.

Fig.1. Bowden FRP bicycle.

Fig.2. Head section (bowden) reinforced by steel plates and pipe.

Fig.3. Seat section (Bowden) reinforced by steelplates and pipe.

Fig.4. Hanger section (Bowden) reinforced by thick FRP ribs.

Fig.5. Microstructure of FRP (Bowden) x33.

Fig.6. Schema of static load test.

Fig.7. Static load-deflection curves of bicycle

Fig.9. Bending load-deflection curves of bicycle

Fig.11. Tensile strength-roughness value of adhered steel joint.

Fig.8. Torsional moment-deflection curves of bicycle (Bowden & Steel).

Fig.10. Roughness curves of mild steel surface polished by various emery papers.

Fig.12. View of fractured surface at adhered zone polished by 600 mesh emery paper. x4

Fig.13. Design of trial manufactured FRP bicycle frame.

Fig.15. Load-deflection (static load test) curves of trial manufactured FRP bicycle.

Fig.14. Trial manufactured FRP bicycle.

Fig.16. Load-deflection (Bending test) curves of trial manufactured FRP bicycle.

Fig.17. Vibration test of FRP bicycle.
Load: 120kg
Revolution: 250r.p.m.

Fig. 11. Vibration test results of trial manufactured bicycle.

Table I. Mechanical properties of various trially manufactured FRP.

Item \ Glass	SLS-213 (Satin)			MG-252 (Loose plain)			A-300 (Twill)		Combination			Combination			Combination		
	SLS-213	CM-305	SLS-213	SLS-213	CM-305	SLS-213	SLS-213	CM-305	SLS-213	CM-305	SLS-213	A-300	RH-400	A-300	A-300	RH-400	A-300
Ply	2	3	4	2	3	4	3	4	1	1	1	1	2		1	1	1
Thickness (mm)	2.0	2.4	3.0	1.8	2.3	2.8	2.6	3.1	3.6			3.5			4.2		
Resin	Unsaturated polyester resin																
Filler	CaCO ₃																
Sclerotic	MEKP																
Accelerant	Co & DMA																
Glass content (wt %)	20.5	23.6	29.2	16.0	18.4	18.6	21.8	21.0	28.5			27.0			25.9		
Tensile strength (kg/mm ²)	25.1 (22.6)	27.5 (24.6)	29.5 (28.0)	12.1 (11.0)	15.5 (11.2)	18.5 (16.5)	21.0 (18.9)	22.0 (19.5)	27.8 (25.6)			25.6 (22.5)			21.8 (19.2)		
Modulus of tensile elasticity (kg/mm ²)	1 800 (1 620)	2 110 (1 950)	2 250 (2 130)	1 200 (1 080)	1 400 (1 180)	1 520 (1 280)	1 600 (1 400)	1 780 (1 520)	1 980 (1 720)			1 620 (1 450)			1 560 (1 330)		
Bending strength (kg/mm ²)	24.8 (22.1)	26.1 (24.5)	31.2 (27.1)	11.8 (10.1)	14.0 (12.8)	17.8 (12.8)	21.5 (19.2)	23.6 (20.8)	30.1 (27.2)			27.3 (25.8)			20.6 (17.8)		
Modulus of bending elasticity (kg/mm ²)	1 850 (1 620)	1 880 (1 650)	1 980 (1 780)	1 250 (1 050)	1 380 (980)	1 520 (1 300)	1 650 (1 400)	1 810 (1 620)	1 890 (1 630)			1 720 (1 480)			1 500 (1 230)		

Table II. Roughness values of polished mild steel surfaces.

Emery No (mesh)	60	120	240	400	600
R _{max} (μ)	15	11	5	1	0.6
Roughness (JIS)	18-S	12-S	6-S	1.5-S	0.8-S